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Project 2

Modelization of heat diffusion in a polycarbonate probe

FYS4096 - COMPUTATIONAL PHYSICS

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1 Introduction

This report is aimed at modelizing a TH 210-R probe, and later on, analyze how the heat of its electronics diffuses through the device.

As the auto-heat generates calories, it can reach the sensitive part of the probe, and thus affects negatively the result of its measurements. We will start by modelizing the heat diffusion, according to the data we've been given and the properties we found on the internet, that are presented in annexe. We are to define the heat points and discuss the optimization of the device's design that would dissipate the calories generated.

Several assumption were made to simplify the simulation, and it is to be said that a model is never exactly representative of the reality. As a result, we must take into account all the simplifications done, in order to analyze our results consistently.

2 Theory

In an electronic device, some components such as chip or power diodes, while operating, produce significant amounts of heat. This production of calories may infer with the reliability of this device's components, and diminish its working life. In the case of a probe, this auto-heat, because of the heat dissipation throughout the device, might also hinder the measurements to be precise.

In our case, this phenomenon is considered to be in an isolated compartment, and thus, will eventually reach an equilibrium when the heat produced becomes equal to the heat lost to the surroundings. The Newton's Law define the rate of heat loss such as proportional to the temperature difference between this component and its surroundings. Thus, as its temperature rises with time, so does the heat loss and when it equates to the heat produced per second within the component, the device will have achieved its equilibrium temperature.

The steady state heat equation of a system ca be found either with or without any heat source in the volume, giving out respectively the following equations :

$$-k\nabla^2 T = q \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla^2 T = 0 \quad (2)$$

k being the thermal conductivity of a material and q being the heat flux per unit of volume.

Nowadays, we try to miniaturize more and more the electronic used, as a result, we also face more and more problems linked to the heat dissipation. Indeed, the components' surface area tending to be always smaller, it follows that for a same input power, the heat flow will be of more importance.

$$q = \frac{P_{dissipated}}{Surface} \quad (3)$$

Its dissipation is done by conduction (two material with different temperatures are in contact, and thus a flow from the hotter to the cooler is created), by convection (heat exchange also from hotter to cooler, but this time between a fluid and a solid) and by

radiation (thermal motion of the particles from a warm object that radiates around it), but this effect will be neglected in this case, as assumed to be less important than the two other phenomenons, and regarding the complexity to find the coefficients needed.

For convection, Newton's law of cooling gives us the heat flow formula :

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = h * A * \Delta T \quad (4)$$

And for conduction, after Fourier's law :

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = \frac{k * A * \Delta T}{L} \quad (5)$$

As heat diffusion problems are made of partial differential equation, one method wildly used is the weak formulation method. Indeed, as partially differential equations are dreadfully difficult to solve, linear algebra, upon which weak formulation relies on, is a good alternative. By tackling the problem under this angle, we can thus solve the diffusion equation and specify the solution using boundaries condition.

We can also sketch the problem under a circuit of resistance, thanks to the analogy between thermal and electric resistance, that both follow Ohm's Law. This can allow a better overview of the problem and how to implement it.

3 Method used

The first step for solving our 3D problem, is to define the coordinates of the system and the boundaries condition. That is what we do in the following figure.

Figure 1: Representative schema of the problem, seen from outside, with its Dirichlet Boundary Conditions

Figure 2: Representative schema of the problem, seen from inside, on the chip side

Knowing we considered the problem to occur under steady-state approximation, We could assume the Dirichlet boundary conditions, shown under thick blue lines in figure 1, as : The temperature of the surface of the sensitive part of the probe is assumed to be the one measured (T_{sample}), and we define the derivative of the temperature on the surface of this same domain to be equal to 0.

Once we had done that, the really next step was to modelize this same model, the probe and its components, on dolfin (FEniCS package). Every part had to be created separately, since, being compound of different materials, the properties of the different components weren't the same, and we needed to make the difference for further calculations. The heat point we consider is the chip only. This assumption was based on the result of an IR camera analysis of the probe while working. We decided to reduce the number of heat points to only this one, to simplify the problem.

Rich of these data, the actual phenomenon of diffusion could be implemented. Having done a similar exercise in class, relative to the heat diffusion of a pan on a stove, it was handy to lean on this. The major difference though was that there were these several components to take into account, through the whole calculation of diffusion. As mentioned in the Theory part , an analogy between thermal and electrical phenomenon can be made, thus, the following figure summarize the problem under the form of an electrical circuit.

Figure 3: Analogy of the heat transfer with electrical resistances

It helped to visualize the extent of the problem in order to be able afterwards to implement it properly. We will do so by considering the phenomenon of conduction (throughout all of the part listed above in the circuit) and convection (done only on the external parts of the device, such as the encapsulation and the probe, both sensitive and non-sensitive parts) within our device.

The weak formulation of the problem was then calculated, based on our boundary conditions (all details for development shall be found in ANNEXE) and its final form is shown in ANNEXE, presented by the equation 9.

The model we implemented is a simple one, relying on several assumption and a more basic geometry, to have a first glance at the actual problem. It could be developed to give out a better approximation of real world physics.

The major assumptions made are listed below :

1. The fact we only considered the chip to be heating up, whereas there were some other components that produced calories, but that we chose to neglect to simplify our model.
2. The geometry was also simplified, as the encapsulation is more complex and that there are way more components, but once again, for us to simplify the problem, it was easier not to consider every single part of the device.
3. Some coefficient weren't known, so they had to be approximated by values found online or substituted by the ones of other material estimated close in the properties considered.
4. We neglected the radiation part, as mention before, as the phenomenon was assumed less intense than convection and conduction parts.
5. We assume the system has reached a steady state and as a result, the temperature does not change with time.
6. The thermal conductivities were assumed to be constant, whereas they might change with temperatures, more particularly with polymers, where k increases with T .
7. The chip was considered as having a really poor efficiency, so that the Power input was practically the Power dissipated.

Following this reasoning, the next part of the task was to implement it in python.

4 Set up and Checking

4.1 Setup

As mentioned in the previous part, the modelization has been made through the `dolfin` package, using Python environment. Only the external domain has been meshed, and the different components and parts of the probe have been defined thanks to the `SubDomain` function, as it seemed easier this way. All of them were marked as boundary or volume units, depending on which aspects we needed in the weak formulation mentioned earlier in this report and presented in ANNEXE. Then, the data obtained through the code were used in Paraview so we could picture the heat flux through our model.

An effort was made also to implement the code in a way that the lengths and dimensions of the components were stored in the first file `probe_meshing.py`. This way, the shapes of objects can be changed merely by inserting the new values in this first file, and the whole modelization adapts to it. Also, the code has been separated into three main files, so its readability would be clearer: a part to define the meshing, one to set up the boundary conditions and the parameters of the problem (such as coefficients and subdomains) and finally a last one where the solution of the partial differential problem was to be solved and the diffusion flux plot.

Once this was done, it was critical to analyze and proceed to some check-up on the results obtained, in order to make sure the implementation was well done and the diffusion graph we got was sensible.

4.2 Checking and Convergence

The main checking done on this simulation was to run a simulation and then verify if there were any convergence between our assumptions and the results obtained. All the data relative to these test can be found in the "test" repository of this project, and the models are also presented in the Result section of this report.

At first, the modelization showed the probe to be colder near by the chip. It made no sense since the chip is the only element taken into account as heating up and thus generating some heat flow. That's how a mistake in the weak formulation was discovered (The heat flow was define as positive whereas it must be negative since it gives out heat

instead of receiving it). Once we solved this problem, we obtained the figure 6, attesting of the heating character of the chip, thanks to a cut into the model, showing the chip as warmer than other component.

Another mistake found thanks to check up was an error in the writing of the coefficients, that led the gradient of temperature to go until -200000°K which was an aberration.

Figure 4: One of the first draft for our model that was clearly wrong

Then, we checked if the implementation was right, by defining the temperature measured at $T_{measured}=-40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the temperature ambient $T_{ambient}=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, if the heat flow was sensible (that the sensitive part of the probe was way colder than the rest of the probe). The corresponding model can be found in the figure 7.

The impact of the ambient temperature as well as the variation of the thermal conductivity coefficients were tested as well, but only the first test is shown (figure 8) in our result section since the test-model relative to the coefficient didn't show very well the relevance of this parameter.

Finally, we checked the heat flow inside the encapsulation thanks to the tool clip in paraview, presented through figure 9. All these results are presented in the next chapter.

5 Results

First, we had the mere meshing of the probe without any diffusion taken into account, as we can see in the following figure.

Figure 5: Meshing of the probe without the diffusion.

(To be noticed that this graph isn't orthonormal). Then, from this model, the weak formulation had to be implemented and apply on the different domains and subdomains of this mesh to describe the heat flux through the device, in function of the boundary conditions defined and the data gathered. The following models were obtained after the test we described in the previous section of this report.

Figure 6: Prove that the chip is indeed the element heating up in our device

Figure 7: Heat flow throughout the probe, with $T_{measured} = -40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{ambient} = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 8: Heat flow throughout the probe, with $T_{measured}=-40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{ambient}=25^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 9: Heat flow throughout the probe, with $T_{measured}=-40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{ambient}=25^{\circ}\text{C}$

All of these presented results are at least in phase with reality : that the encapsulation's temperature relied on the ambient temperature, that the chip heat more with more power, and that the heat diffuses better through the probe with bigger coefficients.

Though there were some short cuts to our model that are to be discussed in the following part.

6 Discussion

First, as we briefly mentioned, our model is a big simplification of the real device, and relies on the boundary conditions and assumptions we made. This means we know it is to present some errors, but even though we were aware of these mistakes to occur, some other problems were encountered and that weren't a result of our assumptions but mainly bugs in our code. All these aspects will be depicted in this section of the report.

The hardest part of this problem was to modelize the heat flux through the probe. The problem was that the chip was considered too small for the mesh to be taken into account, and thus the model couldn't be plotted in Paraview. We had to widen it, even though it meant that the ratio, between the sizes of the components, wasn't correct anymore.

That solved, we encountered minor issues that were fixed thanks to the "logical checking" presented in the Set up Part of this report.

However, by analyzing the figures in the result part, we can see that there were still some problems in our code. For exemple, the figure 9 show an uniform temperature throughout the probe until the sensitive part of it. This shouldn't be, since for example the wire is much more conductive than the other parts, and there should be a demarcation between the encapsulation, circuit and air inside the device. It is to be assumed that these part were, as the chip at first, considered too small by the meshing to be taken into account, and though only the encapsulation was considered. The thermal conductivity coefficient of the encapsulation (ABS) and non-sensitive part of the probe (polycarbonate) are so close that it explains the lack of difference between the two parts. Thus to improve this modelization, a first step would be to find a way to keep the relative ratio between the components (so the model remains correct) but have them considered in the formulation. Also, the lack of precision, either about the coefficient relative to each material, the power dissipated by the chip, the heat point considered, the specific geometry of the device or other components within the probe that were neglected, hindered us to find a real concise answer to our problem to find a way to dissipate the calories provoked by the auto-heat of the electronics. Another statement was that the definition of our boundary condition might not have been the best in our case. Indeed, by assuming that the surface of the sensitive part of the probe is at the same temperature than the sample measured, we cannot see the impact of the calories generated by the electronic, only by the difference

of temperature at the junction (between sensitive and non sensitive part of the probe). And that is not really rigorous as a result.

Despite, this model was logical enough to allow us to consider some of the aspects that could lead us to a solution for the dissipation.

We could see that the difference in temperature as well as the thermal conductivity coefficient are the elements on which relies the heat flow. This same flux that we want to hinder to reach the sensitive part of the probe.

As we cannot really act on the gradient of temperature since this probe is supposed to be able to measure temperature from -40°C to 80°C , in an ambient temperature, the factors we can play with are the following :

1. The thermal conductivity coefficients : like insulate the non-sensitive part of the probe so the heat doesn't reach the sensitive part.
2. Act directly at the basis of the problem : the source of heat.
 - (a) One thing could be to try to diminish the power dissipated by the chip, which is the very source of the auto-heat. For that we could expand its surface, so the heat would be lowered, as we can see it in formula 3.
 - (b) We could also change the material composing the encapsulation and electrical part so it would be less conductive as well.
 - (c) Another solution would be to add up some cooling devices to the model, such as heat sink or Peletier cells. The problem facing these components are respectively that the heat sink would cool down the chip thanks to convection flowing through its fans, though we are in an isolated environment, so there is no real air flow, thus we should design a new model taking that into account. Concerning the Peltier cells, their process of cooling down also produces condensation which would be a problem into the electronic circuit.

Because all of these solution present some negative aspects to be taken into account and fixed, we would have needed a better definition of the problem to elect one of those and concentrate on it.

7 Conclusion

To give a conclusion over this report, we can state that our results rely tremendously on all the assumptions we make and the rigorousness of our definition of the problem. Because in the end, even though our model led us onto the right track to find solutions to the dissipation of calories problem we are facing, its lack of precision hindered us to find a concise one.

Indeed, with a more precise model, we would have got a better insight of the problem, a better range of calories to be dissipated and thus we would have been in a position to define which of the solutions listed above (or even another alternative), would have been best for our problem. Also the definition of the boundary conditions have been proven to be critical in implementation of our model.

As a result, even though we got sensible results, an improvement over the points presented above would give our model much more credit.

8 Annexe

Thermal conductivities and Heat transfer coefficients		
	Thermal conductivity [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Heat transfer coefficient [W.m ⁻² .K ⁻¹]
ABS V0	0.18	
Polycarbonate	0.22	4.1
Inox 316L	16.3	7.9
Circuit (Silicone rubber)	0.14	
Wire	18	
Chip (SiO ₂)	1	
Air	0.025	30

Weak formulation development :

$$-\nabla \cdot [k \cdot \nabla T dV] = \dot{Q} \quad (6)$$

First we multiply by a test function v , and then, we will transform the equation thanks to the Green Theorem. Finally, we will take into account all the coefficient from the different parts and thus get the last equation.

$$\begin{aligned} - \int v \cdot \nabla \cdot [k \cdot \nabla T dV] &= \int v \cdot \dot{Q} \\ - \int k \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV + \int v \cdot k \cdot \nabla T dS &= \int v \dot{Q} dV \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \int_{encapsulation} \mathbf{k}_{encapsulation} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{circuit} \mathbf{k}_{circuit} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{probesensitive} \mathbf{k}_{probesensitive} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{probe-non-sensitive} \mathbf{k}_{probe-non-sensitive} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{airinside} \mathbf{k}_{air} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{wire} \mathbf{k}_{wire} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dS \\
& + \int_{encapsulation} h_{air} \cdot (T_{ambient} - T) dS \\
& + \int_{probe-non-sensitive} h_{air} \cdot (T_{ambient} - T) dS \\
= & - \int_{encapsulation} v \frac{P_{dissipated}}{S_{chip}} dV
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

And thus we can deduce from it the $L(T,v) = b(v)$ formulation needed to solve the

weak formulation and implement it in our code :

$$\begin{aligned}
L(T, v) = & - \int_{encapsulation} k_{encapsulation} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{circuit} k_{circuit} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{probesensitive} k_{probesensitive} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{probe-non-sensitive} k_{probe-non-sensitive} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{airinside} k_{air} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dV \\
& - \int_{wire} k_{wire} \cdot \nabla v \cdot \nabla T dS \\
& - \int_{encapsulation} h_{air} \cdot T dS
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
b(v) = & - \int_{encapsulation} v \frac{P_{dissipated}}{S_{chip}} dV \\
& - \int_{encapsulation} h_{air} \cdot T_{ambient} dS \\
& - \int_{probe-non-sensitive} h_{air} \cdot T_{ambient} dS
\end{aligned}$$

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